
Online Repository 3:

Rapid drug desensitisation protocol for etanercept

Target dose 50 mg

Medicine used

Etanercept 25mg, vials with powder and solvent for injection fluid, (e.g. Enbrel®) .

Reconstructed solutions for injection

Etanercept (Enbrel®) is reconstituted with 1 ml water for injections (sterile water). Chemical and physical stability has been demonstrated for 6 hours after reconstitution at temperatures up to 25°C.

Additional solutions for RDD

Three vials are used: vial A, B and C.

The concentration of reconstructed solution for injection is 25 mg/ml

Dilution α

From vial A, take 0.3 ml (etanercept 25 mg/ml) and add to a sterile vial.

Add 1.2 ml of sterile NaCl to the same vial.

Total volume: 1.5 ml

Concentration: 5 mg/ml

Overall plan for RDD

Seven doses are given at 30 min. intervals.

Steps 1-3 are given from dilution α .

Step 4-7 are given undiluted vials A, B and C

Steps	Dilution	Volumes (ml)	doses	Notes
1	Dilution α	0,1	0,5 mg	
2	Dilution α	0,2	1 mg	
3	Dilution α	0,4	2 mg	Discard the rest of solution α
4	Undiluted, Vial A	0,2	5 mg	Discard the rest of vial A
5	Undiluted, Vial B	0,4	10 mg	
6	Undiluted, Vial B	0,6	15 mg	Corresponding to rest of vial B
7	Undiluted, Vial C	0,66	16,5 mg	Discard the rest of vial C

Observation: 2 hours after last dose.

Subsequent treatment: Injections twice a week with etanercept 25 mg for minimum two weeks. Once tolerated without significant injection site reactions, the patient can proceed weekly injections of etanercept 50 mg.
